

SPIRITUALITY IN THE WRITTEN SOURCES OF THE TURKIC-SPEAKING PEOPLE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7460895>

It is known that dictionary work began in very ancient times, when dictionaries were originally created that were universal in nature, which later branched out in the course of historical progress and today are divided into several dozen types. One of the most common types of linguistic vocabulary in the current period – translation dictionaries that translate and interpret lexical units belonging to the same language into other languages – is a common, long-known type of vocabulary in Uzbek lexicography.

If the famous dictionaries "Devonian dictionary Turk" (11th century), "Prehidimatul Adab" (12th century), "at-tukhfatuz-Zakatsiysky philological dictionary-Turkish" (13th century) were the first Turkish-Arabic and Arab-Turkish dictionaries, then "Badoul-dictionary", "Abushkaa", "Kelurname", "Muntahab ul-dictionary", "Sanglox", "Chagatoi dictionary and Turkish-Ottoman type dictionaries" are dictionaries compiled with the participation of Persian, Turkish and "Chagatoi" (Uzbek) languages.

Consequently, in Uzbek lexicography, bilingual dictionaries created before the beginning of the 20th century were compiled mainly on the basis of linguistic units of the Turkic language (languages), Arabic and Persian (in the case of manuscripts). Indeed, these languages are the main sources of formation and development of the Uzbek language. Our famous poet, hero of Uzbekistan Erkin Vahidov in his book "Speech of the Word" perfectly expressed this situation: "The Uzbek language drank water from three rivers: religious, scientific, social terms mainly from Arabic; many of the names of tools, our words about crafts, words characteristic of the artistic style, came from the Persian language; many military terms, all verbs belong to the Turkic language... The great sea of the Uzbek language drank water from these three Great rivers – the Turkic, Arabic and Persian..." In this book, the Poet repeatedly emphasizes the great importance of Arabic words in the development and enrichment of the Uzbek literary language.

Although at the beginning of the 20th century the Uzbek vocabulary did not create large-scale dictionaries related to the Arabic and Persian languages, a number of works and studies were carried out in this area. At the same time, the work of the famous enlightened Iskhakhan Torr Kazi bin Junaidullah Turakurgani (ibrat) entitled "Sitta Alsina Dictionary" (six-language Arabic-Persian-Turkish-Indian sartcha (Uzbek-Russian dictionary) (Tashkent, 1901) and Salos Saladin Toshkandi dictionary (dictionary in three languages), written in a poetic manner (Aruz) Arabic-Persian-Turkish Dictionary (Tashkent, 1909) can show. These small-volume dictionaries were intended for amateur language learners, Talibi scholars from Madras, who at one time had great cultural and educational significance.

Unfortunately, it was almost impossible to use them en masse due to the fact that the above dictionaries, compiled with the participation of the Arabic language, were distributed by

handwritten or tashbosma (lithographic) method in an extremely small number of copies. That is why Uzbek students studying Arabic, teachers, translators, independent students, even students and teachers of religious schools, religious figures for many years - from the 60s of the last century to subsequent years, Russian orientalist X.K. Those who used Baranov's Arabic-Russian dictionary as the main lexicographic source.

Special difficulties are also observed when using the Baranov dictionary. Russian Russian translation, for example, first of all requires two investments of labor and time, and, moreover, cannot guarantee a full-fledged, high-quality translation result. This dictionary was created during the Shura period and was published several times, for this reason it should be noted that some features of the Arabic language, in particular, Muslim sources that formed the basis of the Arabic language, were overlooked vocabulary, terms of religious literature, the oldest, words, concepts associated with the period of ignorance, etc.

At the same time, during the period from the moment of its publication to the present, science, socio-political life have changed, and thousands of words and phrases have entered circulation in the modern Arabic literary language, giving rise to new phenomena, objects, concepts, many words and phrases have become obsolete and out of use. Therefore, now there is a need to compile a new, original, perfect dictionary using original Arabic sources, as well as the experience of world lexicography.

With a deep understanding of this need, the famous orientalist, academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, public figure of the Republic of Uzbekistan, member of the Cairo Academy of Arabic, Doctor of Philology, Professor Negmatulla Ibragimov and his students - Abdulhakim Oripov, Akmaljon Ikromjonov and Abdulhamid Zairiev have been creating an excellent dictionary since 2012 that could fully meet modern requirements and not need other dictionaries when reading classical texts, and finally completed it with honor in 2022: a four-volume "Al-Komus" consisting of 100,000 words and phrases, as well as a total of 3456 pages. The Arabic-Uzbek encyclopedic dictionary was published in the publishing and printing creative house named after Gafur Gulyam and fell into the hands of its readers in full.

In the "preface" to the 1st volume of the dictionary, it was written about its structure, sources and vocabulary: "when compiling this dictionary, all sources, Arabic and translated dictionaries in Western and Eastern languages were used, the names of which were mentioned in the preface. The dictionary also includes masterpieces of classical and modern Arabic literature, Arabic press, encyclopedias devoted to various fields, scientific research... To him (القاموس [أوزبكي - عربي معجم]) "Al-Komus. The Arabic-Uzbek Encyclopedic dictionary was named". The dictionary embodies words and phrases, terms and concepts that came into use in the most recent period, from the lexicon of ancient times."

It should be said that compiling a dictionary is not an easy task, consisting in simply arranging the vocabulary in alphabetical order and from time to time interpreting it or translating it into any language. On the contrary, it is a complex and painstaking process. In addition to excellent knowledge of a certain language (in this case Arabic), the vocabulary needs kindness, intelligence, hard work and work, work, work again.

Being the product of truly difficult and complicated processes, the dictionary "Al-Komus" with its structure, volume, meaning of words (meanings), the purpose of the heads of verbs, evidentiary (illustrative) examples and other aspects in Arabic-Russian (X. Baranov), Arabic-Uzbek ("An-Naim") differ sharply from dictionaries.

The compilers of the dictionary tried to fully show the vocabulary of the Arabic language in the process of compiling the dictionary, an incredibly large number of synonymous lines in it, the multiplicity of words, and were able to do it completely. They also tried to make the most of their Uzbek alternatives when translating Arabic words and terms into Uzbek and, if necessary, re-created new Uzbek alternatives. Readers who look through the dictionary will witness such news themselves.

Examples of Uzbek literature, in particular, the study of the work of Alisher Navoi, understanding the essence of the ideal Arab-Uzbek, Persian-Uzbek dictionaries that will be created, as well as excellent dictionaries for studying the work of Navoi and other classical writers, are well known to many, especially specialists, in determining the meanings, meanings of certain words from them. Our famous poet Erkin Vakhidov paid great attention to this, and in his book "Dictionary" he gave Talai information about the importance of such dictionaries. He lists 29 dictionaries, such as "Muntahab ul-dictionary", "Bahr ul-Javahir", "burkhoni Kut", "charagi Hidayat", "Gossip ul-dictionary", "Abushka", to which he referred in his studies of classical literature and which are stored in the Treasury of Oriental manuscripts.. The poet also writes about the importance of dictionaries in the study of Navoi creativity: "Every literate person understands well that without seeing a dictionary, our history, centuries-old literature cannot be studied or taught. There is a dictionary of Navoi words that do not fully reflect the vocabulary of Navoi. This imperfect source is also impossible to find in bookstores because it has not been reprinted for many years." Thus, Erkin Vakhidov emphasizes the need for an ideal dictionary for studying the work of Alisher Navoi, for his understanding.

Here is one of the ideal dictionaries that our famous poet dreamed of – "Al-Komus. Arabic-Uzbek Encyclopedic dictionary" in our hands. This dictionary is of great importance not only for the thoughtful study and understanding of the works of Alisher Navoi and other classical poets, their language, but also for the study of more than 100,000 handwritten and stone works stored in various scientific centers of the republic, personal savings and waiting for their researcher, in general, our 1200-year-old written monuments.

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